

Non-extractive spectrophotometric determination of nickel(II) using 2-acetylpyridine thiosemicarbazone/semicarbazone in environmental water samples and alloys

S. Vidyasagar Babu and K. Hussain Reddy*

Department of Chemistry, Sri Krishnadevaraya University, Anantapur-515 003, Andhra Pradesh, India

E-mail : khussainreddy@yahoo.co.in

Manuscript received 01 September 2012, revised 26 March 2013, accepted 08 May 2013

Abstract : 2-Acetylpyridinethiosemicarbazone (APT) and 2-acetylpyridinesemicarbazone (APS) are used as reagents for the spectrophotometric determination of nickel(II) in aqueous medium for the first time. APT and APS react with nickel(II) in acidic and basic medium respectively. The colour reactions between reagents with nickel(II) are instantaneous and the absorbance of complexes remains constant for over 24 h. The maximum absorbance (λ_{max}), composition, molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity of the Ni-APT and Ni-APS complexes respectively are 375, 350 nm; 1 : 2, 1 : 3; 1.6×10^4 , 2.8×10^4 L mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹ and 0.0035, 0.0210 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ of Ni^{II} respectively. The Ni-APT and Ni-APS systems obey Beer's law for 0.47–4.7 : 0.09–0.94 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of Ni^{II} respectively. Large number of cations, anions and complexing agents (e.g. triethanolamine, thiourea) do not interfere in the determination of nickel. The method is successfully applied for the determination of nickel in environmental water and alloy samples.

Keywords : Spectrophotometry, nickel determination, 2-acetylpyridine thiosemicarbazone, 2-acetylpyridine semicarbazone, water, alloy samples.

Introduction

Nickel is both essential element and toxic pollutant for living organisms¹. Many studies showed that the accumulation of nickel in the body through chronic exposure can lead to lung fibrosis, cardiovascular and kidney diseases. The most serious concern is related to its carcinogenic activity². The accumulation of nickel is enhanced with age and smoking. It was confirmed that the tissues of cardiac patients have high level of nickel indicating its possible detrimental effects^{3,4}. Therefore the determination nickel, has great environmental importance. Several workers have reported^{5–7} AAS and ICP-OES methods for nickel determination. However, these methods suffer from limitations such as complicated procedures and costly instrumentation. Spectrophotometric methods are still widely used due to their simplicity and their sensitivity and selectivity depend, on the type of reaction and chromogenic reagent used⁸ in the analytical procedure.

Metal ion determination through solvent extraction suffers from certain inherent disadvantages. Extraction procedures are environmentally undesirable, expensive,

time consuming and tedious. Recently, we have reported spectrophotometric determination of cobalt⁹ using APS and APT. In continuation of our ongoing work^{9–12}, herein we report simple and selective spectrophotometric methods for the determination of nickel in environmental water samples and alloy samples.

Results and discussion

Preparation of APT and APS are reported earlier⁹. The reagent solutions (0.01 M) are stable for 12 h. The bathochromic shift of absorption band from 290 to 300 nm indicates that in solution on increasing the pH, the acid is neutralized and the >C=S group is enolized and dissociated¹³. The colour reactions of some important metal ions with APT and APS are summarized in Tables 1 and 2 respectively.

pKa values : The reagents APT and APS were synthesized as described earlier pKa values of reagents were determined spectrophotometrically by using Phillips and Merrit method¹⁴. The values of deprotonation of APT and APS are 5.47 and 6.61 (pK₁); 8.56 and 8.30 (pK₂)

Table 1. Chromogenic properties of APT

Metal ion	λ_{\max}	$\epsilon \times 10^4$ (L mol ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹)	pH range	Colour of the complex
Cu ^{II}	376	0.26	5.0–7.0	Pale greenish yellow
Ni ^{II}	375	1.6	5.0–7.0	Yellow greenish
Co ^{II}	355	1.25	5.0–8.0	Orange yellow
Zn ^{II}	360	4.06	5.0–7.0	Pale greenish yellow
Fe ^{II}	370	0.17	4.0–7.0	Deep yellow with red tinge
Fe ^{III}	375	0.14	4.0–7.0	Deep yellow with red tinge
Hg ^{II}	351	5.4	5.0–7.0	Yellow coloured
V ^V	360	0.37	3.0–7.0	Yellow coloured

Table 2. Chromogenic characteristics of APS

Metal ion	λ_{\max}	$\epsilon \times 10^4$ (L mol ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹)	pH range	Colour of the complex
Cu ^{II}	355	0.98	5.0–7.0	Yellow
Ni ^{II}	350	2.80	8.0–10.0	Pale pellow
Co ^{II}	360	1.45	5.0–8.0	Orange yellow
Zn ^{II}	355	0.81	5.0–7.0	Greenish yellow
Fe ^{II}	365	0.14	4.0–7.0	Deep yellow with red tinge
Fe ^{III}	370	0.14	4.0–7.0	Deep yellow with red tinge
V ^V	370	0.27	4.0–7.0	Yellow

respectively as shown in Scheme 1. In basic medium the ligands presumably exist in enolic form and coordinates the divalent metal ion as mono anion to give neutral complexes. The chromogenic properties of APT and APS are summarized in Tables 1 and 2 respectively. The colour reactions suggest the potentiality of reagents for the determination of metal ions.

Determination of nickel(II) : The metal ion reacts with APT and APS in acidic and basic pHs respectively to give colored complexes. The colour reactions are instantaneous at room temperature. The change in the order of addition of metal ion, reagent (APT or APS), buffer has no adverse effect on the absorbance of complexes. Absorption spectra of Ni-APT and Ni-APS complexes are given in Fig. 1. Various physico-chemical and analytical characteristics of the complexes are summarized in Table 3. Second derivative spectra of Ni-APT and Ni-APS systems are given in Figs. 2 and 3 respectively. The derivative amplitudes are proportional to concentration of

Scheme 1. Different species of APT and APS in solution at different pH values.

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of Ni^{II}-2-acetylpyridine thiosemicarbazone/semicarbazone complexes : (a) APT vs water blank, (b) Ni^{II}-APT complex vs APT blank, (c) APS vs water blank, (d) Ni^{II}-APS complex vs APS blank.

nickel(II). The composition of complexes are determined by Job's continuous variation, molar ratio methods (Figs. 4–7). Job's curves and molar ratio plots suggest that APT forms 1 : 2 (M : L) complex while APS gives 1 : 3 (M : L) complex. The data obtained in Job's method are used in the calculation of stability constants (Table 3) of the complexes. The stability constant of Ni(APT)₂ is more than that of Ni(APS)₃ probably due to the strong tendency of sulphur donor atom of APT to bind with nickel(II). Structures of nickel complexes are given in Scheme 2.

Table 3. Physico-chemical and analytical characteristics of Ni^{II} complexes with APT and APS

Sl. No.	Characteristics	Results	
		Ni(APT) ₂	Ni(APS) ₃
1.	λ_{\max} (nm)	375	350
2.	pH range (optimum)	5.0–7.0	8.0–10.0
3.	Mole of reagent required per mole of metal ion for full colour development	10 fold	10 fold
4.	Time stability of the complex (in min)	12 h	75
5.	Beer's law validity range ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	0.47–4.70	0.094–0.94
6.	Molar absorptivity ($\text{L mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$)	1.6×10^4	2.8×10^4
7.	Specific absorptivity ($\text{ml g}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$)	0.284	0.479
8.	Sandell's sensitivity ($\mu\text{g of Ni}^{\text{II}} \text{cm}^{-2}$)	0.0352	0.021
9.	Composition of the complex as obtained in Job's and molar ratio methods (M : L)	1 : 2	1 : 3
10.	Stability constant of the complex	1.84×10^{14}	1.32×10^{14}
11.	Standard deviation in the determination of 1.20 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of Ni ^{II} for ten determinations	0.0094	0.0144
12.	Relative standard deviation (RSD), (co-efficient of variation) (%)	0.032	1.024

Fig. 2. Second derivative spectra of Ni^{II}-APT vs reagent blank Ni^{II}, $\mu\text{g/ml}$; (a) 0.9381; (b) 1.8762; (c) 2.8142; (d) 3.7523; [APT] = $4 \times 10^4 \text{ M}$; pH = 6.0.

Interference : The effect of various cations and anions which are generally associated with the metal ion on the determination of nickel(II) is studied by measuring the

Fig. 3. Second derivative spectra of Ni^{II}-APS vs reagent blank Ni^{II}, $\mu\text{g/ml}$; (a) 0.1876; (b) 0.3752; (c) 0.5638; (d) 0.7505; [APS] = $6 \times 10^4 \text{ M}$; pH = 9.0.

Fig. 4. Job's curve, Ni^{II} = APT = $1 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$ (stock solution), wavelength = 375 nm, pH = 6.0.

Fig. 5. Molar ratio plot, [Ni^{II}] = $1.2 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$, wavelength = 375 nm, pH = 6.0.

absorbance of the nickel complex in the presence of foreign ions. The colour reaction is developed as described

Fig. 6. Job's curve, $Ni^{II} = APS = 2 \times 10^{-4} M$ (stock solution), wavelength = 350 nm, pH=9.0.

Fig. 7. Molar ratio plot, $[Ni^{II}] = 2.4 \times 10^{-5} M$, wavelength = 350 nm, pH = 9.0.

in the recommended procedure given in Experimental section. An error of $\pm 2\%$ in the absorbance or amplitude reading (in the case of derivative methods) is considered tolerable. The results are given in Table 4. The data obtained in second derivative method are also incorporated. The data suggest that several associated anions and cations do not interfere when they are present in large excess. The tolerance limit values for many anions and cations are high in derivative methods. The interference of associated metal ions such as Fe^{III} and Al^{III} is decreased with triethanolamine. Larger amounts of copper(II) do not interfere in the presence of thiourea.

Applications : The present methods are successfully applied to the determination of nickel when present alone. The APS method is used in the determination of nickel in a number of environmental water samples. The amount

Table 4. Tolerance limit of foreign ions in the determination of 2.4 ($\mu g/ml$) of nickel

Ion	Tolerance limit (ppm)			
	Zero order		Second order	
	APT	APS	APT	APS
Triethanolamine	1250	1120	1450	1350
Citrate	1152	460	1360	480
Acetate	280	460	300	480
Nitrate	310	250	320	270
Sulphate	380	230	400	250
Oxalate	530	210	550	230
Tartrate	600	360	620	380
Iodide	510	410	530	430
Carbonate	360	290	380	310
Bromide	320	200	340	220
Thiourea	430	190	450	210
Fluoride	80	70	100	90
Fe^{IIIb}	6.0	6.0	8.0	8.0
Cu^{IIa}	1.8	2.5	2.0	2.7
Hg^{II}	4.8	4.8	5.0	5.0
Co^{II}	0.7	1.4	1.0	2.4
Zn^{II}	0.8	3.6	1.1	3.8
Al^{IIIb}	6.5	0.8	10	1.0
Cd^{II}	27	27	29	29
Mg^{II}	5.0	4.0	11	8.0
Cr^{VI}	12	1.3	22	2.8
Mo^{VI}	23	2.3	42	4.6
P^{II}	11	2.6	13	2.8

^aMasked with 400 $\mu g/ml$ of thiourea. ^bMasked with 1000 $\mu g/ml$ of triethanolamine.

of nickel is determined in aluminum based alloys using APT. Data are given in Tables 5 and 6 respectively.

Table 5. Determination of nickel(II) in water samples

Sample	Nickel ^a ($\mu g L^{-1}$)		Recovery (%)
	Added	Found	
Waste water	0	1.21	-
	100	102.41	101.18
	500	502.30	100.21
Sea water ^b	0	2.12	-
	100	102.10	99.98
	500	501.90	99.95
Laboratory ^c	0	123.00	-
	100	218.20	97.84
	500	615.40	98.78

^aA verage of five determinations. ^bBay of Bengal, Chennai. ^cS. K. University, Chemistry Department Lab Water.

Experimental

The reagent (APT or APS) solutions (0.01 M) were prepared by dissolving 50 mg of the compound in

Table 6. Deterimination of nickel(II) in aluminum based alloys and alloy steel samples

Sample	Cetr. comp. (%)	Amount of nickel(II) (%)		Relative error (%)
		Present	Found ^a	
Aluminum based alloys :				
BAS-20	Cu 4.10; Ni 1.93; Fe ^b 0.43; Mn 0.19; Si 0.29; Mg 1.61; Rest Al	1.93	1.91	-1.03
BAS-85	Cu 0.90; Ni 0.91; Fe ^b 1.15; Mn 0.02; Si 2.04; Mg 0.18; Zn 0.01; Rest Al	0.91	0.93	-2.19
Alloy steel samples :				
Copper-nickel alloy	Cu 67; Fe 0.83; Mn 0.083; Si 0.29; Ni 31.21	31.20	31.32	+0.38
Alloy NTPC ball bearing :				
Material	Fe 65; Cr 15; Cu 4.5; Mn 2; Ni 10.00	10.00	9.96	-0.40
BCS 364	Cu 80.00; Sn 9.35; Pb 9.25; Ni 0.28; Sb 0.18; Zn 0.13; As 0.065; P 0.056; Al 0.002; Si 0.003	0.280	0.278	-0.71
Gun metal	Zn 1.37; Sn 9.22; Cu 87.95; Pb 1.13; Fe 0.01; P 0.07; Ni 0.24	0.240	0.242	+0.84
Monel	Ni 63.01; C 0.15; S 0.002; Mn 0.07; Si 0.05; Fe 2.50; Cu 31.0	63.10	63.20	+0.16

^aAverage of five determinations.

dimethylformamide (DMF) in 25-ml standard flask. The reagent solutions are stable for at least 12 h.

Hydrochloric acid (1 *M*)-sodium acetate (1 *M*) (pH 0.5–3.5); 0.2 *M* NaOAc-0.2 *M* AcOH (pH 4–6) and 2 *M* NH₄Cl-2 *M* NH₄OH (pH 7–10) solutions were used in the present study.

Nickel(II) solution : NiSO₄·7H₂O (0.281 g) was dissolved in doubly distilled water containing a few drops of conc. H₂SO₄ in a 100-ml standard flask to get a 1 × 10⁻² *M* solution. The stock solution was standardized gravimetrically using diethylglyoxime¹⁵. The working solutions were prepared daily by diluting the stock solution to an appropriate volume. All other chemicals used were of AR grade.

Recommended procedures : An aliquot of the solution containing nickel(II) in Beer's law validity range (Table 3) and buffer solution in optimum pH range and 1 ml of

0.01 *M* reagent (APT or APS) were combined in a 25-ml volumetric flask and the resulting solution was diluted to the mark with distilled water and absorbencies were measured at absorption maximum against corresponding reagent blank. The measured absorbance is used to compute the amount of nickel present in the samples using predetermined calibration plot. The effect of foreign ions was studied similarly by adding the foreign ion before the addition of reagent solution.

Determination of nickel in environmental water samples using APS method : Water sample (250 ml) was filtered through Whatman No. 40 filter paper. Then it was mixed with 10 ml of concentrated nitric acid in a 500 ml distillation flask. The sample was digested in the presence of an excess potassium permanganate solution according to the standard procedure¹⁶. The solution was cooled and neutralized with dilute ammonia solution. The digest was

transferred into a 25-ml calibrated flask and diluted up to the mark with de-ionized water. The amount of nickel in different water samples was estimated by using recommended procedure.

Determination of nickel in aluminum based alloys and alloy steel samples using APT method : About 0.4 g alloy sample (BAS-20, BAS-85) was treated with 15 ml of 1 : 1 HCl and 3 ml of HNO₃. The contents heated to obtain residue which was dissolved in 10 ml of water and 40 ml of 4 N ammonium hydroxide solution and filtered through a Whatman filter paper (No. 41). The filtrate was collected into 25-ml volumetric flask and made up to the mark with distilled water.

Known aliquot of the above alloy sample solution was taken in a 10 ml flask containing 5 ml of buffer solution (pH 6.0), 70 µg/ml of fluoride to mask Fe^{III} and 1 ml of the APT solution (1 × 10⁻² M). The contents were made up to the mark with distilled water and the absorbance of the resulting solution was measured at 375 nm against the reagent blank. The amount of nickel(II) present in the sample was determination from the predetermined calibration plot.

Determination of nickel(II) using second derivative spectrophotometry : A sensitive second order derivative spectrophotometric method was developed for the determination of nickel(II). In the second derivative spectra of

Scheme 2. Tentative structure of (a) [Ni(APT)₂]²⁺, (b) [Ni(APS)₃]²⁺ complexes.

Ni-APT and Ni-APS, the derivative amplitudes at 434 nm, 403 nm (peak) and at 498 nm, 440 nm (valley) respectively were proportional to the concentration of Ni^{II}. The derivative amplitudes were measured for different concentration of Ni^{II}. Calibration plots were prepared between the amplitude and the amount of Ni^{II}. The plots were linear and obeyed Beer's law in the range 0.2135–0.0088, 0.2437–0.0026 µg ml⁻¹ at 434 nm, 403 nm and 0.1063–0.0054, 0.1579–0.0016 µg m⁻¹ at 498 nm, 440 nm respectively.

Apparatus : Shimadzu 160A UV-Visible spectrophotometer equipped with 1.0 cm quartz cell and an ELICO model LI-610 pH meter were used in the present study.

Conclusions

The present methods for the determination of nickel(II)

Table 7. Comparison of spectrophotometric methods for the determination of nickel

Name of the reagent	λ_{\max}	pH	Determination range (µg/ml)	$\epsilon \times 10^4$ (L mol ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹)	M : L	Refs.
Diacetylmonoxime-4-phenyl-3-thiosemicarbazone (DAMOPT)	355	2.0–6.0	0.45–2.35	1.75	1 : 1 and 1 : 2	17
1-Phenyl-1,2-propanedione-2-oxime thiosemicarbazone (PPDOT)	395	3.0–6.0	0.42–3.76	1.01	1 : 2	18
2-Hydroxy-3-methoxybenzaldehyde thiosemicarbazone (HMBAT)	410	4.0–8.0	0.058–2.347	2.05	1 : 1	19
4-Methyl-2,3-pentanedione dioxime (H ₂ MPDDO)	370	9.0	0.5–10	3.039	1 : 2	20
4-Hydroxybenzaldehyde-4-bromophenylhydrazone (4-HBBPH)	497	2.0–4.0	0.01–0.1	1.285	–	21
2-Acetylpyridine thiosemicarbazone (APT)	375	5.0–7.0	0.47–4.70	1.6	1 : 2	PM
2-Acetylpyridine semicarbazone (APS)	350	8.0–10.0	0.094–0.94	2.8	1 : 3	PM

PM - Present methods.

are compared with other recently reported spectrophotometric methods¹⁷⁻²¹. The present APS method seems to rank among highly sensitive methods for the determination of nickel(II). The results obtained in the analysis of different samples using present method are comparable to the data obtained (Table 7). The present ligands containing heterocyclic ring are found to be potential and cost effective for the determination of nickel(II) without the need for extraction and toxic solvents. Further, the reagents are easy to synthesize using commercially available precursors. Moreover, the present methods are simple, rapid and very sensitive for non-extractive spectrophotometric determination of nickel(II) in aqueous medium.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (SVB) is thankful to UGC, New Delhi for award of Post-Doctoral Research Fellowship. The authors also thank UGC and DST, New Delhi providing equipment facility under UGC-SAP and DST-FIST programs respectively.

References

1. A. Vercruyse, "Hazardous Metals in Human Toxicology", Part B, Elsevier, New York, 1984, p. 13.
2. G. Scansetti, G. Maina and G. C. Botta, *International Archives of Occupational and Environmental Health*, 1998, **71**, 60.
3. A. Vienna, E. Capucci, M. Wolfsperger and G. Hauser, *Anthropologischer Anzeiger*, 1995, **53**, 27.
4. E. Denkhaus and K. Salnikow, *Crit. Rev. Oncology/Hematology*, 2002, **42**, 35.
5. M. Gonzalez, M. Gallego and M. Valcarcel, *Talanta*, 1999, **48**, 1051.
6. D. Zendelovska, G. Pavlovska, K. Cundeva and T. Stafilov, *Talanta*, 2001, **54**, 139.
7. A. E. Vereda, R. F. Sanchez, A. K. Chakrabarti, A. Garcia de Torres, J. M. Cano Pavon and Fresenius, *J. Anal. Chem.*, 1991, **340**, 262.
8. E. B. Sandell, "Colorimetric Determination of Traces of Metals", 3rd ed., Interscience Publishers, New York, 1959.
9. S. Vidyasagar Babu, K. Hussain Reddy and Y. Lingappa, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2009, **86**, 1.
10. D. Nagarjuna Reddy and K. Hussain Reddy, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2011, **88**, 595.
11. N. B. L. Prasad and K. Hussain Reddy, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2007, **84**, 474.
12. K. Vasudeva Reddy, S. Vidyasagar Babu and K. Hussain Reddy, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2009, **86**, 162.
13. B. A. Gringas, R. L. Somojai and C. H. Bayley, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1961, **39**, 973.
14. J. P. Phillips and L. L. Merritt, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 410.
15. A. I. Vogel, "A Textbook of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 5th ed., Longman, 1989, p. 327.
16. F. W. Fifield and P. J. Haines, "Environmental Analytical Chemistry", Blackwell Science, 2000, p. 378.
17. N. B. L. Prasad, PhD thesis, S. K. University, Anantapur, 2001.
18. N. B. L. Prasad and K. Hussain Reddy, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2004, **81**, 794.
19. A. Preveen Kumar, P. Raveendra Reddy and V. Krishna Reddy, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2007, **46**, 1625.
20. J. Garole Dipak and A. D. Sawant, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 2005, **64**, 581.
21. D. Rekha, J. Dilip Kumar, B. Jayaraj, Y. Lingappa and P. Chiranjeevi, *Bull. Korean Chem. Soc.*, 2007, **28**, 3.

